

Synthesis of Terpyridines: Simple Reactions – What could Possibly Go Wrong?

Dalila Rocco, Catherine E. Housecroft and Edwin C. Constable *

University of Basel, Department of Chemistry, BPR 1096, Mattenstrasse 24a, CH-4058 Basel,
Switzerland; dalila.rocco@unibas.ch; catherine.housecroft@unibas.ch;
alessandro.precimone@unibas.ch

Figure S1. Electrospray mass spectrum of 5a.

Figure S2. Electrospray mass spectrum of 5c.

Fig. S3. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) spectra of (a) **5a** and (b) **5c**. * = CDCl_3 .

Fig. S4. IR spectrum of solid **5a**.

Fig. S5. IR spectrum of solid **5c**.

Fig. S6. IR spectrum of solid **6b**.

Figure S7. Electrospray mass spectrum of **6b**.

Figure S8. NOESY spectrum of **6b** (500 MHz, CDCl₃, 298 K).

Figure S9. HMQC spectrum of **6b** (500 MHz, CDCl₃, 298 K).

Figure S10. HMBC spectrum of **6b** (500 MHz, CDCl₃, 298 K).

Figure S11. Electrospray mass spectrum of **6a**.

Figure S12. Electrospray mass spectrum of **6c**.

Figure S13. IR spectrum of solid **6a**.

Figure S14. IR spectrum of solid **6c**.